

The Influence of Leadership Style and Organizational Culture on Performance at The Education Office of the Labuhan Batu District with Competence as an Intervening Variable

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ABSTRACT: Performance appraisal is an important need to be able to measure the extent of the progress and development of the organization, whether it is in line with the process of change that occurs in its internal human resources. This performance assessment cannot stand alone, but is related to the formation of strategies that lead to the achievement of the vision, mission and goals of the organization, for this reason it is necessary to find opportunities for the organization to make improvements and innovations through the formation of a strategy. This study aims to determine whether leadership style and organizational culture affect employee performance through competence as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu Regency Education Office. The results obtained in this study indicate 1) there is a significant influence between leadership style on competence, 2) there is a significant influence between organizational culture variables on competence, 3) there is a significant influence between leadership style variables on performance, 4) there is a significant influence between organizational culture variables on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between competency variables on performance, 6) competency variables cannot influence leadership style variables on performance, 7) competency variables can influence organizational culture variables on performance.

KEYWORDS: Competence, Leadership Style, Organizational Culture, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources or employees play an important role in achieving goals for a company or organization. This is one effort that can be done by carrying out employee performance appraisals. Gibson et al (2009), argued that the task of human resource management is part of management that focuses on elements of human resources with their potential so that satisfied and satisfying resources can be obtained for the organization. Good human resource management is the key to success in achieving agency or organizational goals.

However, based on the results of preliminary research at the Labuhan Batu District Education Office, there is a difference between expectations and reality. The phenomenon seen in terms of employee competence is that most employees do not have the desire to continue their education to a higher level, are unable to interact properly and there are employees who are unable to carry out tasks assigned by superiors.

The leadership that occurred at the Labuhan Batu Regency Education Office was considered quite good, because every task given to the leadership could be carried out properly and produced good results as well. The leadership of the Labuhan Batu Regency Education Office also gives full authority and responsibility to employees in carrying out their duties and obligations. However, in terms of supervision it is still not good, because the leadership of the Labuhan Batu District Education Office rarely supervises employees properly in carrying out their daily work, the punctuality of employees in working and the punctuality of employees in completing the tasks assigned to them. Leaders also have not been able to show their role in creating innovations that are useful for organizational development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Performance

Performance is very important to ensure the achievement of the goals expected by the organization. By the organization. In organizations, performance is often used as a benchmark to assess whether or not organizational goals are achieved. The better the individual performance of the organization, the faster the organizational goals will be achieved.

The definition of performance is the result of a process that refers to and is measured over a certain period of time based on predetermined provisions, standards or agreements (Lubis, et al, 2018: 26).

There are thirteen factors that influence performance, namely:

Ability and skills, Knowledge, Work design, Personality, Work motivation, Leadership, Leadership style, Organizational culture, Job satisfaction, Work environment, Loyalty, Commitment, Work discipline.

An employee's performance can be influenced by intrinsic factors such as knowledge, skills, abilities, confidence, motivation, commitment, and extrinsic factors, namely: leadership, work environment, teamwork, work system, duties and responsibilities, pressure and changes in the internal and external environment of the organization (Fauza, 2010; Yamin & Maisah, 2010: 129).

2. Competence

Competence is a person's ability to carry out his job carefully and correctly, or in other words to understand and master the skills he should do (Lubis, et al, 2018: 53).

According to McClelland in Jimmy (2014: 499) defines competence as a fundamental characteristic that a person has that has a direct effect on, or can predict, excellent performance. Meanwhile, Palan (2007: 6), says that competence consists of several different types of characteristics, which drive behavior. The foundation of these characteristics is evident in the way a person behaves in the workplace. Competence is about what kind of person and what they can do, not what they might do. Competencies are found in people who are classified as superior or effective performers.

There are several factors that can affect a person's competency skills, which are as follows:

Beliefs and values, Expertise or skills, Experience, Personal characteristics, Motivation, Emotional issues, Intellectual capacity, Organizational culture.

Relevant Previous Research

Previous research is very important as a basis for preparing this research. The following are the results of previous research.

Table 2.1 Previous Research

Num ber	Name/ year	Title	Research Variables	Research Results
1.	Syamsu Alam (2019)	The Effect of Competence and Organizational Culture on Performance through Work Discipline of Employees of Makassar Polytechnic of Pelayara Science	Independent: Competence (X1) Organizational Culture (X2) Dependent: Performance (Y) Intervening: Work Discipline (Z)	Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Makassar Polytechnic of Shipping Science, Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Makassar Polytechnic of Shipping Science.
2.	Jamaluddin, Rudi Salam, Harisman Yunus and Haedar Akib (2017)	The Effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the South Sulawesi Provincial Education Office The Effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at the South Sulawesi Provincial Education Office	Independent: Organizational Culture (X) Dependent: Performance (Y)	From the results of the product moment correlation analysis, a significant level of relationship was obtained between the influence of organizational culture on employee performance at the South Sulawesi Provincial Government Education Office in the Strong category.

3.	Aan Rahman and Siti Marfina Esterina (2018)	Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Performance	Independent: Leadership Style (X) Dependent: Performance (Y)	The results of the study found strong relationship between leadership style and employee performance.
4.	Umar Makawi, Normajatun and Abdul Haliq (2015)	Analysis of the Effect of Competence on Employee Performance of the Banjarmasin City Industry and Trade Office	Independent: Competence (X) Dependent: Performance (Y)	The results show that competence affects performance.
5.	Happy Y. Mogot (2019)	The Effect of Leadership Style, Work Ethic, Competence and Work Discipline on Employee Performance at PT PLN Manado Branch.	Independent: Leadership Style (X1) Work Ethic (X2) Competence (X3) Work Discipline (X4) Dependent: Performance (Y)	The results showed that partially the Leadership Style had no significant effect on Employee Performance at PT PLN Manado Branch.

The Effect of Leadership Style on Competence

In achieving its goals, every organization is influenced by organizational behavior which is a reflection of the behavior and attitudes of the actors contained in the organization, be it leaders or subordinates. The leader usually has his own traits, ways and styles which are characteristic so that his behavior and style distinguish him from others. This style or style of life will definitely color the behavior and type of leadership.

The Effect of Organizational Culture on Performance

In order to improve the performance of qualified and professional employees, one of the factors suitable for implementation in the work environment is organizational culture. Organizational culture can help employee performance, because it creates an extraordinary level of motivation for employees to give their best ability to take advantage of the opportunities provided by their organization. To implement a suitable organizational culture in an organization, it is necessary to have the support and participation of all members within the scope of the organization.

To make it easier to explain a study, the researcher describes a conceptual framework that contains the relationship between variables as follows:

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

A hypothesis is a temporary answer to research problems, until proven through the data collected. The hypotheses of this study are:

- H1: Leadership style has a significant effect on competence.
- H2: Organizational culture has a significant effect on competence.
- H3: Leadership style has a significant effect on performance.
- H4: Organizational culture has a significant effect on performance.
- H5: Competence has a significant effect on performance.
- H6: Leadership style has a significant effect on performance through competence.
- H7: Organizational Culture has a significant effect on performance through Competence.

Research Design

This research is included in associative research with a quantitative approach. This study examines the relationship between the variables of Leadership Style (X1) and Organizational Culture (X2) on the Performance variable (Y) with Competence (Z) as an intervening variable. In this study, the approach used is a quantitative approach because the data used to analyze the effect between variables are expressed by numbers or numerical scales (Kuncoro, 2011, in Wulandari, 2015).

Operational Design

The operational definition of research is a further description of the definition of concepts that are classified in the form of variables as instructions for measuring and knowing whether the measurement is good or bad in a study. The operational definitions in this study are as follows:

Table 3.1 Operational Definition Table

Variable	Defenition	Indicator	Measurement Scale
Performance (Y)	Real behavior that everyone displays as a work achievement produced by employees according to their role in the agency. Performance is very important in an agency's efforts to achieve its goals.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Quality 2. Quantity 3. Time (Long term) 4. Supervision 5. Relationship between coworkers 	Likert
Competence (Z)	The ability and willingness to perform a task with effective and efficient performance to achieve company goals.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Beliefs and Values 2. Skills 3. Experience 4. Personality Characteristics 5. Motivation 6. Intellectual Ability 7. Organizational Culture 	Likert
Leadership Style (X1)	One of the ways used by a leader in influencing, directing and controlling the behavior of others to achieve a goal.he process of influencing or pushing from	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ability to make decisions 2. Ability to motivate 	Likert

	the outside towards a person or work group so that they want to carry out something that has been determined.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Ability to control subordinates 4. Responsibility 5. 5.Ability to control emotional 	
Organizational Culture (X2)	Organizational culture is the norms and values that direct the behavior of organizational members. Because of course every member of the organization has its own personality that distinguishes it, (Luthans, 2010, p. 122).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Behavioral rules observed 2. Standard norms of behavior 3. Dominant value 4. Philosophy 5. Rules 	Likert

The Effect of Leadership Style on Competence

The leadership style variable has a positive and significant effect on competence at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The leadership style variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.141 has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the leadership style variable will increase the value of the competence of the Labuhanbatu Education Office employees by 0.141 per one unit score.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that leadership style has a significant influence on the competence of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is supported by research conducted by Happy Y. Mogot, Christoffel Kojo and Victor P K Lengkong (2019), revealing that leadership style has an influence on competence.

The Effect of Organizational Culture on Competence

Organizational culture variables have a positive and significant effect on competence at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The organizational culture variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.078 has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the organizational culture variable will increase the value of employee competence at the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.078 per one unit score.

Based on the results of testing the second hypothesis, it is known that organizational culture has a significant influence on the competence of Labuhanbatu Education Office employees. This is supported by research conducted by Jamaluddin, Rudi Salam, Harisman Yunus and Haedar Akib (2017), revealing that organizational culture has a significant influence on competence.

CONCLUSION

- a. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on competence at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that leadership style can improve employee competence.
- b. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on competence at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that organizational culture can improve employee competence.
- c. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that leadership style can improve performance.
- d. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that organizational culture can improve employee performance.
- e. Competence has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that the better employee competence can improve performance.

- f. The effect of leadership style on employee performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office will be smaller if done through competence. The direct effect of leadership style on employee performance is greater than the indirect effect of leadership style on performance. It can be concluded that competence is not able to mediate the effect of leadership style on performance.
- g. The effect of organizational culture on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office will be greater if done through competence. The direct effect of organizational culture on performance is smaller than the indirect effect of organizational culture on performance. It can be concluded that competence is able to mediate the effect of organizational culture on performance.

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